

**“ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: A BREAKTHROUGH ON THE
PATH OF PROGRESS OR A SOURCE OF DANGER?”**

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Annotation.

This article explores the positive and negative aspects of artificial intelligence in the context of rapidly developing modern technologies. Since AI is becoming an integral part of everyday life and plays an important role in problem-solving and decision-making processes, the study pays particular attention to its influence on society. To identify current attitudes and opinions, a detailed survey was conducted among university students, and the article is based on the results of this research.

Keywords:

Artificial intelligence (AI), technology, innovation, assistance, positive aspects, negative aspects, survey, students, impact.

Introduction.

In recent years, artificial intelligence technologies have been considered one of the developments in science, technology and human history. Today's informatization processes are accelerating so much that in this situation, before humanity can accept and assimilate AI or reject it, it continues to serve as an integral part of everyday life. Artificial intelligence, or in short, AI, has now managed to solve not only simple and simple human problems, but also to think broadly and comprehensively on important and relevant topics, and partially perform mental activity. The main purpose of this article is to study the advantages and possible

negative aspects and criticisms of intelligence in real practice, to conduct a deep analysis based on the opinions of students and young people, and to formulate promising and useful conclusions for the future.

Positive aspects of AI

Increases work efficiency

Today, artificial intelligence serves as an important and key factor in increasing work efficiency in many industries (Brynjolfsson & McAfee, 2017). Also, through AI, there is an opportunity to analyze and illuminate data extensively, which helps to increase working time and productivity in organizations and enterprises. Due to the time saved, monthly salary expenses are also significantly reduced. Various errors are sharply reduced in industries where a large number of workers operate through the AI system. With the help of AI, people have more time to think, innovate, and work on themselves.

Application in medicine

Medicine is an integral part of human life. With the help of AI, serious and dangerous diseases can be diagnosed quickly and accurately. Also, AI deeply analyzes images - visual examinations such as X-ray, MRI, MSCT, CT - and helps determine the necessary treatment measures (Topol, 2019). In addition, it is also used as an important assistant in the continuous monitoring of conditions such as blood pressure, heart rate, and blood sugar levels.

Application in education

One of the main pillars of the modern world is education. AI has a wide role in distance learning systems and online classes. AI improves the quality of lessons and helps to quickly find the necessary topics. In addition, AI acts as a personal teacher for each student, taking into account the knowledge and skills of the student (Luckin et al., 2016). Being an important assistant to teachers, AI quickly analyzes and accurately evaluates written work and tests.

Negative aspects of AI

Job reduction

Although the widespread introduction of artificial intelligence technologies increases economic efficiency, it can also reduce jobs. Because automated techniques perform many tasks faster and cheaper. As a result, many workers in manufacturing are being replaced by machines (Frey & Osborne, 2017). This increases the risk of financial instability in society.

Spread of false or misleading information

AI has the potential to create content on a large scale. However, this process can often lead to the spread of incorrect information (disinformation). In political processes, the spread of false information can affect election results, and in medicine, it can pose a threat to human health (Zeng, Lu & Huangfu, 2022).

Psychological dependence and weakening of critical thinking

The excessive use of AI has a negative impact on human thinking. People begin to prefer virtual conversations to real communication. As a result, critical thinking and independent decision-making skills are weakened (Carr, 2020). This reduces the ability to be creative and solve problems independently.

So‘rovnoma natijalari

Kelajakda AI odamlar hayotini yaxshilaydimi yoki yomonlashtiradimi?
22 ОТВЕТА

1. Will AI improve or worsen people's lives in the future?

As can be seen from the diagram, the largest proportion of respondents (45.%) predict that AI will have both positive and negative aspects in the future. 36.4% of

respondents think that it will mainly improve people's lives. Only 13.6% could not express their clear opinion on this issue. This result shows that, although there is some concern among people about the future impact of artificial intelligence on people, there is also concern.

Sizningcha, sun'iy intellekt hayotimizni osonlashtiradimi?
22 ОТВЕТА

2. Do you think artificial intelligence will make our lives easier?

The results show that the majority of respondents (50%) believe that artificial intelligence will make everyday life much easier. 45.5% said that it will only help a little. A very small minority think that it will not help at all. This result shows that people have high hopes for AI.

AI ta'lim jarayonida foydali deb hisoblaysizmi?
22 ОТВЕТА

3. Do you think AI is useful in education?

According to the survey results, the majority of participants (63.6%) believe that AI is a great help in education. 18.2% consider it to be somewhat useful. Also, 13.6% think that it is not useful at all. These results indicate that AI is being positively perceived in education.

Sizning fikringizcha, AI ish o'rinlarini qisqartirish xavfini tug'diradimi?

22 ОТВЕТА

4. Does AI pose a risk of job losses?

According to the results, a large majority of respondents (45.5%) believe that AI will eliminate some jobs and create new ones. 40.9% said that many jobs will disappear and opportunities will be limited. 13.6% believe that some jobs will appear in more areas. In this case, there is no clear consensus among people. So, opinions within society remain diverse.

AI'ning qaysi salbiy tomonini ko'proq xavfli deb o'ylaysiz?

22 ОТВЕТА

Question 5: What negative aspect of AI do you think is dangerous?

According to the survey results, the largest proportion of respondents (45.5%) consider the threat to the security of personal data and its misuse as the main problem. (40.9%) These figures indicate that they expressed their opinion on the widespread spread of false and inaccurate information in society and the emergence of negative events. 13.6% believe that AI weakens human thinking. This result shows that people are seriously thinking about the negative consequences of AI and security issues.

Conclusion

The results of the article and the survey results show that artificial intelligence, along with creating great opportunities for the future of humanity, also poses significant risks. AI makes everyday life easier, increases efficiency in education and medicine. However, there are risks such as misuse, job losses, and psychological dependence. Therefore, supporting safety and social justice is essential for the effective use of AI.

References

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lova 1. Survey questions about artificial intelligence (AI) among students

1. Specify your age group.
2. Your gender.
3. Your current status (study/position).
4. When did you hear about artificial intelligence (AI)?
5. Do you think artificial intelligence will make our lives easier?
6. Do you think AI is useful in the educational process?
7. Do you think AI poses a risk of job losses?
8. In which field would you like to use AI more?
9. Which negative side of AI do you think is the most dangerous?
10. Do you think AI can reduce human creativity?
11. How do you think students should use AI?
12. Will AI improve or worsen people's lives in the future?
13. What precautions do you think should be taken when using AI?